

- CLEWS Model in Bolivia: NDC Goals and Biodiesel Scenarios

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Keywords

CLEWs, OSeMOSYS, renewables share, Hydropower, Biodiesel

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study explores an integrated systems approach for Bolivia using the Climate, Land, Water, Energy nexus framework and the OSeMOSYS modelling tool. Three scenarios were analyzed—Business as Usual, NDC (Nationally Determined Contributions), and Biodiesel—to assess their impacts on the interaction of CLEWS.

The analysis highlights that achieving Bolivia's NDC goals is heavily reliant on hydropower expansion, requiring a 240% higher investment compared to the Business as Usual scenario to meet targets by 2030. Considering the extended timelines required for hydropower project development, early actions are essential. Regarding Biodiesel scenario, increased biodiesel production may result in higher CO₂ emissions and reduced forest cover, potentially conflicting with national deforestation prevention goals. This aspect should be further explored in future studies.

INTRODUCTION

Bolivia has long depended on natural gas as its primary energy source and one of the main income sources. At the same time, Bolivia is highly vulnerable to the effects of climate change, making it the most affected country in South America and the tenth most at risk globally [1], with severe droughts and eventual floods, affecting among other sectors agriculture activities. On the other hand, approximately 200,000 rural households

in Bolivia still lack reliable access to electricity. The electricity coverage in urban areas in Bolivia is 99,2% whereas the coverage in rural areas is 81.5%. In regions like Pando and Beni, rural electrification is even lower, reaching only 70%. This situation has negative repercussions on health, household safety, access to basic services such as clean water and sanitation, adequate healthcare, as well as on education and employment opportunities [2]. and committed to its NDC goals, which include mitigation and adaptation targets across sectors such as energy, forestry, water management, and agriculture [1].

Given these interconnected goals and challenges in Bolivia, a CLEWS (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems) analysis is essential. The CLEWS framework provides a holistic approach to evaluating the impacts of strategies across sectors, ensuring that decisions on energy, land use, and water management align with the country’s climate and development goals. For Bolivia, where natural resources are closely interlinked, and both energy dependence and climate vulnerability are high, a CLEWS analysis can guide more balanced and sustainable policy-making, helping the country transition to a resilient and low-carbon future.

This study will explore the Bolivia’s energy system, and how it will evolve by 2070 including energy NDC goals, but also a project for biodiesel that is planned by the government, and the interaction of both with climate land water energy nexus.

METHODOLOGY

CLEWS methodology is applied to analyze the interactions of climate, land, water, energy nexus in Bolivia, using OSeMOSYS model. Figure 1 represent the Bolivian CLEWS diagram considered in the study. The primary energy resources considered are natural gas, solar radiation, wind, water and biomass. Land output resources included in the model are soybean, maize, sorghum and sugarcane.

Figure 1: Bolivia's reference CLEWS diagram

The energy data was sourced from CCG's Starter Data Kit for Bolivia [3], Land data was collected from multiple sources, including Our World in Data [4] FAOSTAT [5] while water data was obtained from AquaSTAT [6]. Additional information was drawn from Bolivia's NDC [1], governmental plans [7] and scientific papers cited below.

Three scenarios were investigated using the CLEWS methodology, described in Table 1, with the corresponding key assumptions:

Table 1: Scenario Description and Key assumptions

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Business as Usual	CLEWS for 2070 including generation capacity from ongoing projects by 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constant installed capacity in thermoelectric power plants. • Biomass electricity generation potential limited to 19.22 PJ [8].
NDC Scenario	NDC Goals by 2030: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1st: 79% of electricity generation from Renewables • 2nd: Including a 19% Share from Wind, Solar, and Biomass. • 3rd: Total installed Capacity of 5.03 GW 	Electricity Demand increase of 67.8 PJ to meet 3 rd NDC goal
Biodiesel Scenario	Biodiesel production of 723,4 million liters/year by 2025 [7]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiesel generation from soy bean crops. • The demand of biodiesel is projected to increase according to population growth. • Emissions for biodiesel=emission of diesel for agriculture. • Output activity ratio is 6 PJ/MMTon Soybean

RESULTS

This model exercise explored the following research question:

How will Bolivia's energy system and its climate-land-water-energy nexus evolve by 2070, considering **NDC energy targets** and a **biodiesel project**?

In the Baseline scenario, the main technologies for electricity generation are thermal power plants and hydro power plants. To meet the increasing demand by 2070 investments are needed in hydro, wind and biomass technologies. Regarding NDC goals, the renewables share in 2030 in this scenario is 43.24 %. Land area covered by forest decreases by 4.83 % from 2020 to 2070. Most of the land crops will be rainfed.

Figure 2: Power Generation for the BAU Scenario (left) and the NDC scenario (right)

The NDC scenario to accomplish the three energy goals, will need an increase in hydropower capacity by 109.7% by 2030, with an investment of 240% higher than the Baseline scenario and 9% higher CO2 emission.

Figure 3: Installed capacity for the BAU scenario and the NDC Scenario

Table 2: Results Comparison of BAU Scenario and NDC Scenario

	BAU Scenario	NDC Scenario
Investment by 2030 (MM USD)	1737	5912 (240% higher than BAU)
CO2 Emissions MMTon (accumulated from 2020 to 2070)	259.65	283.03 (9% higher than BAU)
Water Demand for power sector billions m3 (accumulated from 2020 to 2070)	39.7	39.7

For the biodiesel scenario, to meet the biodiesel production goals for 2025, the area dedicated to soybean crops needs to increase by 141.7% compared to the baseline. This expansion will result in a 78.62% rise in agricultural land and a 3.2% reduction in forested areas. Consequently, diesel consumption for agriculture will increase by 76% compared to the baseline. As most crops will be rainfed, this will lead to an accumulated increase in CO2 emissions of 10.2% relative to the baseline.

Figure 4: Area by crop in the Biodiesel Scenario (left) and a comparison of the new area for soybean crops with BAU Scenario (right)

Table 3: Results comparison for the BAU Scenario and the Biodiesel Scenario

	BAU Scenario	Biodiesel Scenario
Land Area covered by Soybean crops 2025 (1000 sq.km.)	15.14	36.58 (141.68% higher than BAU)
Land area for agriculture 2025 (1000 sq.km.)	27.27	48.71 (78.62% higher than BAU)
Forest Area (1000 sq.km.)	675.03	653.58 (3.2 % lower than BAU)
Diesel Demand (PJ)	2.25	3.96 (76 % higher than BAU)
CO2 Emissions MMTon (accumulated from 2020 to 2070)	259.65	286.03 (10.2% higher than BAU)

DISCUSSION

In the Baseline scenario, Bolivia's significant hydropower potential makes it the most cost-effective and suitable option for electricity generation, given that it is a renewable resource. Additionally, electricity generation from biomass residues is a promising alternative. However, the expansion of agricultural land driven by the preference for rainfed farming as a more economical option leads to a reduction in forested areas. This shift is facilitated by the extensive land availability in Bolivia.

Figure 5: Generation Capacity Comparison of BAU Scenario and NDC Scenario, considering only the accomplishment of the 1st and 2nd NDC goals

The NDC scenario requires new investments primarily in hydropower plants. However, it is crucial to account for the time required for these plants to be constructed and become operational. Additionally, meeting all three targets will demand increased investments, not only to satisfy domestic energy needs but also to generate electricity for export. If only the first and second targets are met, focusing solely on domestic electricity demand, the required increase in hydropower installed capacity will be 87 % (Figure 5), investment will be 131% higher than the baseline. Under this scenario, the cumulative emissions over the study period (2020-2070) will be 1.86% above the baseline, while the cumulative water demand for the power sector during the same period will be 20.53% lower than the baseline.

Table 4: Results Comparison of BAU Scenario and NDC Scenario, considering only the accomplishment of the 1st and 2nd NDC goals

	BAU Scenario	NDC Scenario 1 st 2 nd GOALS
Investment by 2030 (MM USD)	1737	4007 (131% higher than BAU)
CO2 Emissions MM Ton (accumulated from 2020 to 2070)	259.65	264.49 (1.86% higher than BAU)
Water Demand for power sector billions m3 (accumulated from 2020 to 2070)	39.7	31.55 (20.53% lower than BAU)

The Biodiesel scenario suggests a reduction in forest area, potentially conflicting with Bolivia's deforestation prevention objectives. Additionally, the increased use of diesel for agricultural purposes, which is currently subsidized, requires careful evaluation as it could impact economic and environmental sustainability.

Given the assumptions made, a more detailed representation of the energy and agricultural systems is recommended. For instance, only four crops were modelled, but incorporating a broader range of crops could provide a more comprehensive analysis.

Enhanced data collection from governmental institutions could further improve the accuracy of these projections.

It is important to take into account how the proposed energy scenarios interact with other NDC goals. These include reducing deforestation by 80% from the baseline, increasing forest cover by one million hectares by 2030, expanding efficient irrigation to 1.3 million hectares, and restoring degraded soils.

A valuable area for future research lies in the modelling of multipurpose water reservoirs that serve both energy and non-energy needs, such as irrigation and drinking water. This could be achieved by integrating an electricity dispatch model like Dispa-SET, which allows for cross-sectoral analysis, followed by incorporating WEAP to predict future water availability under climate change scenarios. This combined approach would significantly enhance the comprehensiveness and robustness of the analysis.

CONCLUSION

Achieving Bolivia's three NDC energy goals requires a substantial 109.7% increase in hydropower capacity, translating to an estimated investment of 5.9 billion USD by 2030. Given the significant timelines for the planning, construction, and commissioning of hydropower plants, careful coordination and early action are essential to meet these targets.

Expanding biodiesel production from soybeans would necessitate a 141.7% increase in soybean cultivation, which could result in a 9.4% rise in CO₂ emissions and a 3.2% decrease in forest cover. To ensure sustainable growth, this expansion must be aligned with Bolivia's deforestation reduction commitments, highlighting the need for balancing bioenergy development with environmental conservation objectives.

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